

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Monetary Policy Performance under Control of exchange rate and consumer price index

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Abstract

Central Reserve announced the Monetary Policy Rate and equally interested in the output of exchange rate and price stability. Besides having a stabilizing effect on the price level and trend of exchange rate stabilized the countries outputs. This Study adopts Generalized Method of Movements (GMM) for panel data; to examine the monetary policies stability effect due to changes in Inflation, and Exchange rate. We use monthly data for seven World important countries which covering globally; United States, United Kingdom, Switzerland, Sweden, Denmark, Japan and India for the period of 1955 to 2021. We find that monetary policy control; the price level does not affect production and exchange rate. Monetary policy is the only thing that can change the trend of exchange rate and Consumer Price Index. The actual policy was fixed exchange rate, and currency devaluations like Japan were quite successful for stability. The results indicate that the central bank can stabilize much of the macroeconomic indicators and disturbances under a monetary exchange rate and consumer price index system.

Keywords: Central Bank Policy Rate; Monetary Stability; Consumer Price Index; Exchange Rate

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1.Introduction

This journal aims to ask whether Central Bank Policy Rate is a cause of the low real interest rate on safe assets since the onset of the Covid 19 crisis. The Central Reserve usually it's a low-interest rate when it wants to stimulate the economy. But many researchers attribute the low real interest rate to fundamental factors. Such factors

lead to associate with expected lower economic growth in future. Actual rates where common causes future growth is the expectation of being low. Caused by Fed policy was the low-interest rate in the United States and worldwide. This article exploits the research area of Central Bank Policy Rate Regimes to shed light on the most critical issue. From 1965 to 2021, the central Reserve operation Central Bank